

Bio Knowledge Agora: Developing the Science Service for
European Research and Biodiversity Policymaking

D7.4. Final Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
BAK	Biodiversity Knowledge Agora
DEC	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
KCBD	EU Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results
SPI	Science-Policy Interface
SPSI	Science-Policy-Society Interface
SSBD	Science Service for Biodiversity
TCC	Transformative Change Cluster

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE BIOAGORA PROJECT

BioAgora is a collaborative European project funded by the Horizon Europe programme. It aims to connect research results on biodiversity to the needs of policy making in a targeted dialogue between scientists, other knowledge holders and policy actors.

Its main outcome will be the development of a Science Service for Biodiversity. This new service will fully support the ecological transition required by the European Green Deal and the European Union's Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

The BioAgora project was launched in July 2022 for a duration of 5 years. It gathers a Consortium of 22 partners, from 13 European countries, led by SYKE, the Finnish Environment Institute. Partners represent a diversity of actors coming from academia, public authorities, SMEs, and associations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is deliverable of the BioAgora project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101059438.

Deliverable 7.4 presents the final version of BioAgora's Final Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results of BioAgora (PDEC). This comprehensive document builds on previous iterations (D7.1 and MS7.1), consolidating the project's outreach achievements to date and laying out a forward-looking strategy for the final phase of the project and its legacy.

The core focus is on enabling the successful uptake, institutional integration and long-term sustainability of BioAgora's flagship result: the Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD), which is positioned as the scientific pillar of the EU Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBD).

The PDEC provides an evaluation of progress in M1-M36 of BioAgora's communication and dissemination activities.

Key updates in this final PDEC aligned with the classification of target groups used by other work packages and developed tailored engagement pathways for each. The PDEC provides dedicated communication and dissemination roadmaps for:

- knowledge providers (e.g. researchers, research networks), including knowledge-brokering mechanisms;
- knowledge users (e.g. EC DGs);
- interest groups (e.g. non-governmental organisations (NGOs), business actors, media).

This plan also outlines a strategic implementation plan for M36-M60, featuring revised Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and new tools, such as the SSBD digital dashboard, targeted factsheets, key SSBD explanatory video, stakeholder testimonials and success stories. This strategic implementation plan also includes a special section on bilateral communication, dissemination and exploitation (DEC) engagement with priority organisations through the co-creation of joint DEC materials and initiatives, visibility actions and knowledge mobilisation.

The envisioned actions in this document aim to provide a clear pathway for BioAgora's future DEC actions, which would aim to ensure that the project is well-positioned for the SSBD's launch and long-term exploitation. A promotion strategy (D7.3) and a business plan for the SSBD (D4.3) will follow to ensure continuity and institutional anchoring post-2027.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

The BioAgora project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme, aims to establish the Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD) as the key mechanism to link EU research and biodiversity policymaking. Over the course of the project, DEC activities have played a significant role in engaging target groups, amplifying the project’s visibility, and ensuring that its results reach and serve their intended audiences.

This final PDEC presents a consolidated vision of BioAgora’s outreach and legacy. It builds upon the strategic direction laid out in the Initial PDEC (D7.1), its mid-term update (MS7.1) and integrated feedback from project reviewers, aligning all efforts with BioAgora’s Key Exploitable Result (KER) - the SSBD.

Between M1-M36, BioAgora successfully transitioned from establishing communication and dissemination channels and initial awareness-building to active stakeholder engagement, working through customised communication tools such as the project website, newsletter, social media, policy briefs and a growing network of events. Key milestones include:

- mapping existing Science-Policy-Society Interfaces (SPSIs);
- proposing a governance model for the SSBD, including an ethical risk assessment;
- establishing an active dialogue with key EC representatives;
- setting up the answering requests process;
- developing active Knowledge Exchange Networks (KENs) on Pollination, Nature-based solutions, Freshwater, Multifunctional landscapes, Monitoring and scenarios, Transformative change, and Marine topics;
- facilitating the development or long-term perspective of clusters of EU funded projects; such as the Marine Cluster or the Transformative Change cluster;
- creating synergies with other relevant initiatives such as Biodiversa+, Eklipse, Oppla, the CO-OP4CBD and RESPIN projects, the Montpellier Process;
- launching the website’s Synergies section;
- promoting and disseminating the first two BioAgora cascade funding calls;
- organising key events for both knowledge users and providers (including an online information event attended by more than 150 attendees representing over 70 EU projects and initiatives, as well as two joint side events at the UN CBD’s COP16 in October 2024);
- Representing and presenting BioAgora and the future Science Service at multiple events in order to get the buy-in from the broader community;
- Supporting initiatives proposed by the community to assist the Science Service for Biodiversity, such as new bottom-up KENs led by non-partners of BioAgora.

Looking ahead, this PDEC outlines how BioAgora’s main results, particularly the Science Service and stakeholder networks, will continue to be promoted, integrated, and sustained beyond the project’s lifetime. It also presents updated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), target audiences and lessons learned to support future exploitation and maximise the project's long-term impact on biodiversity governance in the EU.

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1. Introduction

The final PDEC outlines the strategic and operational approach of the BioAgora project to ensure that its final outputs, generated knowledge and SPSI innovations are effectively shared, adopted and sustained. As a Horizon Europe-funded initiative, BioAgora plays a pivotal role in strengthening the SPSI for biodiversity in Europe by establishing the SSBD - a key mechanism for bringing biodiversity knowledge to EC policymakers.

Communication, dissemination and exploitation have been central pillars of BioAgora's implementation strategy since the project's inception. BioAgora's DEC activities have been defined within the relevant EU guidelines for EU-funded projects, namely as:

- Communication – to inform, promote and communicate activities and results to citizens, stakeholders and the media (European Commission, 2023). The role of communication is to spread project activities and results in a way that they are accessible and understandable by multiple audiences, including the public, and acts in support of dissemination activities.
- Dissemination – to make results available publicly and free-of-charge for those who can learn and benefit from results, such as scientists, policy-makers, public authorities, industry and civil society (European Commission, 2023). Dissemination is a more targeted approach, referring to sharing research results with potential users, i.e., peers in the research field and members of the scientific community, industry, commercial agents and policymakers.
- Exploitation – the actual use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes by stakeholders such as scientists, policymakers, industry, public authorities, and civil society (European Commission, 2023). Exploitation is the use of results in further research and innovation activities, including, improving policies and tackling economic and societal problems at hand.

The project's outreach efforts were first formalised in the Initial Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (D7.1), which laid the foundations for engagement with key stakeholder groups. This was followed by an Updated Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (MS7.1) at M24, reflecting a shift from awareness-building to more targeted, participatory engagement in response to evolving project needs and reviewer feedback.

The present final PDEC brings this strategic arc to its conclusion by consolidating past actions and setting a forward-looking path for sustaining BioAgora's impact. It presents an integrated overview of DEC activities carried out during the first three years of the project (M1 - M36). Based on this assessment, it defines how BioAgora's main outcome - the SSBD including its Biodiversity Knowledge Agora stakeholder network - will be fully activated in the final phase of the project and beyond its duration. The plan reflects on lessons learned, engagement outcomes and the evolution of target audiences and outlined engagement strategies.

Within this deliverable, an update of BioAgora's key messages and dissemination pathways is provided, with the specific task to outline the strategic DEC actions until the end of the project's duration and beyond the end of the project's lifetime. The final PDEC provides a strategy on the most efficient pathways for articulating BioAgora's legacy within the broader EU biodiversity governance and knowledge system, including its alignment with the KCBD and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

In doing so, this final PDEC provides not only a record of BioAgora’s outreach achievements, but also a practical roadmap for the long-term exploitation of its results by policy-makers, researchers, civil society and institutional stakeholders.

1.1. Evaluation of progress (M1-M36)

SECTION SUMMARY

This section provides a comprehensive assessment of BioAgora’s progress in implementing its DEC strategy since the beginning of the project, taking into account the foundation provided by the Initial Plan (D7.1) and the progress reported in its mid-term update (MS7.1). It evaluates both the quantitative and qualitative dimensions of outreach efforts across all stakeholder categories, drawing on predefined KPIs, stakeholder feedback and project monitoring data.

The development of BioAgora’s strategy for the forthcoming period is informed by a comprehensive evaluation of activities carried out during the project’s first 36 months. It builds on successful experiences and integrates lessons learned from all relevant actions. The summary below outlines BioAgora’s DEC activities undertaken between M1-M36, accompanied by an assessment of progress against the project’s established key performance indicators (KPIs) (Table 1).

Table 1: Evaluation of BioAgora DEC activities, M1-M36

Tool	Target group	Action in M1–M36	Target for M1–M36	Achieved result in M1-M36	Analysis / justification
BioAgora website	All	<p>M5-24: Conceive, design and integrate a project website, following this by intensive promotion and updating of internal content via new articles, publications, campaigns, etc.</p> <p>M24-36: Update the website to create new features, including "Frequently Asked Questions" (FAQ) section and Synergies pages</p>	<p>Users: 6000+</p> <p>Geographical scope: 50+ countries</p>	11 754	<p>The BioAgora website as the main channel of DEC activities is a platform for intensive promotion of the project’s developments in all aspects of its activities.</p> <p>Throughout M1-M36, the website has been updated multiple times to feature new elements relevant to the work of BioAgora.</p> <p>New sections such as the Synergies page, the FAQ page and the activation and development of the Cascade Funding page have been developed to accommodate the project’s needs.</p> <p>Furthermore, to support increase of outreach, the BioAgora website now integrates both a translation tool and an accessibility tool.</p>
Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Bluesky	All	<p>M1-M24: Establish a stable online presence via concrete and comprehensive posting plans incorporating dynamic campaigns introducing the key facets</p>	<p>Total followers (M60): 1000 (X), 750 (LinkedIn)</p>	<p>Total followers achieved (M36): 688 (X)* 295 (Bluesky) 1,306 (LinkedIn)</p>	<p>LinkedIn has consolidated itself as the primary platform wherein BioAgora stakeholders and partners are engaged, reaching 150% of the set KPI on followership.</p>

Tool	Target group	Action in M1–M36	Target for M1–M36	Achieved result in M1-M36	Analysis / justification
		<p>of the project</p> <p>M24-M36: Create more synergies on social media with other key stakeholders (a particular focus on creating a set of communication clusters, with the initiatives and european projects that are part of the Knowledge Exchange Networks</p>		<p><i>* This number is the one of the remaining followers. The BioAgora X profile is deactivated and currently there is only a landing page redirecting to other social media.</i></p>	<p>Prior to November 2024, BioAgora’s X account amassed a following comparable to the target number (982). However, the network on the whole suffered a substantial exodus of users in the time since. This tendency, coupled with an evidently questionable moderation and ethical policy direction by X’s management, resulted in a consortium-wide decision to leave the platform.</p> <p>Bluesky was chosen as a replacement as it is quickly becoming a vibrant hub for the scientific communities of Europe. In the span of under 6 months, BioAgora’s profile has enjoyed a substantial following when compared to other research project accounts on the network. As the platform develops, new opportunities to expand the project’s reach will be pursued.</p>
Promotional materials	All	<p>M1-M24: Create foundational promotional materials - poster, banner, QR code(s)</p> <p>M24-M36: Create new promotional materials - sticker, brochure, factsheet, policy brief</p>	<p>150 downloads/item 50 distributed/per event</p>	<p>250 downloads (~65 per item) ~ 50 distributed/per event</p> <p>Distributed materials: -project one-pager -QR code sticker -Newsletter subscription form: in conjunction with CO-OP4CBD and TRANSPATH -SPSI project brochure: in conjunction with CO-OP4CBD, RESPIN and TRANSPATH -project poster -project roll-up banner Distributed at all events listed further below in Section 1.1</p>	<p>BioAgora’s promotional materials have benefitted from wide distribution, both online and at the numerous internal and external events where the project has been in focus. A consistent standard of quality was ensured by virtue of both their sustainable production and the numerous updates they received so as to reflect the evolving realities of the project.</p> <p>The downloads per item targets have not achieved throughout the period between M1-M36. This is due partially because of the taking into account of the fact that the launch of the project website was in M5, and as with time progresses, more promotional materials have been added to the section.</p>
BioAgora Newsletter	All	<p>M1-M24: Create a dedicated project newsletter summarising project aims and developments in a succinct and visually appealing manner</p>	5 newsletters	<p>Achieved: 5</p> <p>Stakeholder categorisation of subscribers: -policy- and decision-makers (45)</p>	<p>With 469 subscribers, the project newsletter is now a primary dissemination channel whose content reaches beyond the BioAgora consortium.</p> <p>Researchers, stakeholders and policy-makers are the recipients of this</p>

Tool	Target group	Action in M1–M36	Target for M1–M36	Achieved result in M1-M36	Analysis / justification
		<p>M24-M36: Create new sections for the newsletter, focusing on scientific news relevant to policy and vice versa (e.g. spotlight on proceedings at COP16, developments surrounding the EUPB, etc.)</p>		<p>-scientists and experts (171) -interest groups and general public (63) -other BioAgora partners and EU-funded projects (190)</p>	<p>output, being informed on the project's progression and achievements. Moreover, dedicated sections of the newsletter now outline news relevant to the broader biodiversity SPSI landscape in Europe and beyond. Dedicated section with updates from the EUPB has been created and a dedicated section with key developments by other initiatives (including synergies with BioAgora) has been also featured.</p> <p>In addition to the 4 project-specific newsletters, a joint issue on CBD/COP16 was prepared in conjunction with the CO-OP4CBD project.</p>
Press relations and media coverage		Submit press releases covering critical project developments on established science communication platforms (AlphaGalileo and EurekAlert!)	5 press releases	<p>Achieved: 6 press releases</p> <p>“New project to serve biodiversity science to decision-makers”</p> <p>“Four Horizon Europe funded projects to host key side events at UN CBD COP16, highlighting the role of science-policy interface in biodiversity and climate change”</p> <p>“BioAgora and NINA announce new Cascade Funding Call for Science-Policy-Society Interface (SPSI) Capacity Development Initiatives”</p> <p>“Key side events from UN CBD's COP16 now available online: Discussion on the role of the science-policy interface in biodiversity”</p> <p>“The first BioAgora Cascade Funding Call concludes with two winning proposals”</p>	<p>In addition to an introductory press release showcasing the project's purpose and objectives, BioAgora also disseminated a press release on the first Cascade Funding Call and two press releases on its participation at CBD/COP16 Colombia in conjunction with RESPSIN, Biodiversa+ and CO-OP4CBD.</p> <p>Finally, the conclusion of the first and the launch of the second Cascade Funding Call for third parties were also covered in this manner.</p>

Tool	Target group	Action in M1–M36	Target for M1–M36	Achieved result in M1-M36	Analysis / justification
				Second Cascade Funding Call press release	
Policy briefs		M1-M36: Issue one policy brief	4 policy briefs for the entire project duration	Achieved: N/A	The first BioAgora policy brief was produced, however, due to strategic dialogue on the overall role of policy briefs in BioAgora, its publishing was postponed.
Videos		Create new video content with a focus on the SSBD	5 videos 800 views on YouTube	Achieved: 8 Views: 1000 BioAgora: Connecting biodiversity knowledge with decision-making BioAgora 2022 Highlights BioAgora's consortium meeting in Leipzig (11-12 October 2023) BioAgora 2023 highlights BioAgora Information Event "Connecting Biodiversity Knowledge & Decision-making", 16 April 2024. BioAgora Webinar "Introduction to the BioAgora Science Policy Interface pilot training", 6 May 2024. BioAgora at COP16: Discussion on the Science-Policy Interface (SPI) Landscape (Side Event 1) BioAgora at COP16: SPI Contribution to Biodiversity, Health & Climate Change (Side Event 2)	An introductory video was produced to showcase the essence and approach underpinning the BioAgora project. An overview of BioAgora's second annual consortium meeting in 2023 was also publicised on YouTube. An edited recording of the BioAgora information event was published as well. The same was done for 2024's webinar on the BioAgora SPI pilot training. Following the organisation of two side events with RESPSIN, Biodiversa+ and CO-OP4CBD at CBD/COP16 Colombia, the CO-OP4CBD and the BioAgora YouTube channels distributed recordings of those two sessions. Three annual highlights videos have also been produced for BioAgora outlining the project's progress.
Events (organised)		Organise events aiming to promote the functions of the project as well as develop and enhance capacities of researchers, stakeholders and decision-makers at the biodiversity SPSI.	4 events for the entire project duration	Achieved: 9 <i>A full list of the organised events can be found further below in Section 1.1.</i>	Throughout the implementation period and in conjunction with other EU-funded projects and key initiatives (incl. SAFEGUARD; CO-OP4CBD; Biodiversa+ and RESPSIN), BioAgora conducted workshops, interactive exercises and trainings on a variety of

Tool	Target group	Action in M1–M36	Target for M1–M36	Achieved result in M1-M36	Analysis / justification
					topics associated with the biodiversity SPSI knowledge flows and how they are meant to feed into the future SSBD. While a number of those were held independently, the majority among them were conducted as side events complementing international conferences.
Conferences		Participate in different conferences and forums, at which project outputs and the functions of the SSBD are to be presented	20 conferences	Achieved: 29 A full list of the attended international conferences and partner events can be found further below in Section 1.1.	Throughout the project's first three years, BioAgora was consistently in the spotlight at international fora and conferences addressing biodiversity in general and its myriad sub-themes and associated topics. As a result, a wide audience numbering in the thousands was directly exposed to BioAgora messaging, promotional materials and SPSI-related outputs.
Factsheets		M1-M60: Create factsheets to be issued throughout the duration of the project	10 factsheets for the entire project duration	Achieved: N/A	Work on the first BioAgora factsheet (based on D2.1) has already begun, with a designed draft pending final approval.
Infographics		M1-M36: Create a new infographic, describing the project's core functions	1 infographic	Achieved: 5 infographics produced	Two infographics describing the BioAgora functions and the answering requests function have been developed in the initial phase of the project, and have been applied in multiple BioAgora presentations. Three infographics (based on D2.3) have been produced in M35 with the aim to provide support to the dissemination of results on the BioAgora assessment of the transformative potential of networks. A BioAgora design of the scientific pillar of the KCBD was produced as well as and two infographics on the functions and answering requests function. A new infographic describing the project's core functions is drafted and finalised within WP7 to provide a more general overview of the SSBD's place in the EU biodiversity SPSI landscape.

Within the period of M1-M36, BioAgora conducted a number of key DEC high-impact actions, which served to showcase the project’s development and promote the main KER that the project is meant to provide - the SSBD. These activities included:

1. **Improving the DEC strategies and delivering timely and well-structured information on the project developments** (demonstrated by a steady stream of news items, sustained engagement with BioAgora content across social media platforms, and a growing base of newsletter subscribers reflecting a consistent outreach effort);
2. **Producing and disseminating the BioAgora project video alongside maximising visibility of flagship events** (such as the COP16 side events and the BioAgora Info Event - through the editing and publication of high-quality video recordings);
3. **Advancing the project’s core communication tools and infrastructure, including ongoing improvements to the BioAgora website to accommodate the evolving needs of the Science Service** (notable developments include the creation of dedicated pages for Synergies and FAQs, technical upgrades to the Cascade Funding section, and the redesign of the Knowledge Exchange Networks space to function as dedicated microsites for individual networks (in progress));
4. **Strengthening collaboration within the Transformative Change Cluster (TCC) of EU-funded projects** (through coordinated communications efforts, the establishment of a continuous exchange mechanism, reciprocal participation in events, and the co-organisation of a joint communications campaign for the International Day of Biodiversity 2025, led by BioAgora);
5. **Fostering synergies with CO-OP4CBD and RESPIN, through a coordinated communication workflow aimed at maximising outreach and coherence** (this includes both digital collaboration and the production of shared promotional materials such as a joint brochure and a harmonised newsletter subscription form for distribution at relevant events);
6. **Maintaining alignment with key communication partners to ensure consistency of messaging and reinforcement of shared objectives** (including IPBES, the UN CBD, Eklipse, and Biodiversa+);
7. **Showcasing BioAgora at major international policy arenas to reinforce the project’s presence in global biodiversity and climate governance discussions** (including UN CBD COP16, UNFCCC COP29 and high-level side events of the 61st Plenary Session of the IPCC).

A notable highlight in the first part of BioAgora’s development is the participation of the project in a wide array of high-impact conferences and forums. BioAgora was involved in and organised a series of events of different types with the aim to increase the project’s visibility and provide insights into the role of the future SSBD in the biodiversity SPSI. A list of the notable examples is provided below.

1. Organised sessions at conferences and forums

- a. Participation in a **TCC Workshop** organised by the EC’s Research Executive Agency (17 March 2023): in-person workshop for a number of Horizon Europe projects contributing to Transformative Change for Biodiversity;
- b. BioAgora session at the **2023 Radboud Conference** (22-27 October 2023): the session focused on how BioAgora may support transformative change in the European biodiversity policy arena;
- c. BioAgora **Information Event for EU-funded projects** (16 April 2024): online event with over 150 participants with the aim to provide information on the opportunities that the SSBD provides to knowledge providers;
- d. BioAgora at the **2024 World Biodiversity Forum** (17-18 June 2024): BioAgora hosted two sessions at this important global summit. The first was titled “Closing the Social-Ecological Loop: From Principles to Practice” and presented various aspects of the integration of social-ecological systems to create holistic approaches for assessing and managing biodiversity changes. The second BioAgora session

was co-organised together with the KCBD and was titled “Converting Biodiversity Knowledge into Actionable Knowledge: A Glimpse into the New Biodiversity Knowledge Governance in Europe”. It delved into the complexities of converting scientific evidence into actionable knowledge for policy-making;

- e. Co-organisation of 2 joint side events at **UN CBD’s COP16** (21 October - 1 November 2024) – a synergy between BioAgora, CO-OP4CBD, RESPIN and Biodiversa+ which aimed to showcase the different aspects of the solutions that the science-policy interface (SPI) for biodiversity brings to the table to support biodiversity policy in the EU and beyond;
- f. Co-organised session of BioAgora, CO-OP4CBD and RESPIN at the **2025 Altnet Conference** (13-16 May 2025);
- g. Co-organised session at the 2025 **SAM Conference** (27 May 2025) – together with the Montpellier process and INRAE, BioAgora conducted a session on 27 May titled [“Making the Case: Forward-looking Science-Policy-Action Interfaces for Tackling Nexus Challenges Across Scales, Sectors and Actors”](#).
- h. Launch of marine biodiversity cluster event – co-organisation and hosting of session, (13-14 April 2025).

2. Interactive workshops organised

- a. Online interactive workshop on the [transformative potential of networks in agroecology](#) (21 February 2025);
- b. Interactive workshop on [biodiversity policy and citizen science](#) – 5th ECSA Conference (3 April 2024);
- c. Interactive workshop on [marine biodiversity](#) – SRI Conference (13 June 2024);
- d. Interactive [roleplay workshop](#) at ESEE Degrowth Conference (18 June 2024);
- e. Collaborative workshop on [freshwater management](#) – SERE 2024 (25 August 2024).

3. Presentations at EU-funded project meetings

BioAgora has also been presented at a wide array of EU-funded project meetings, both with promotional materials and oral presentations. This includes project meetings of TETTRIs, SELINA, CO-OP4CBD, RESPIN, B3, SpongeBoost, ANERIS, REST-COAST, BIONEXT, SHOWCASE, PollinERA, Safeguard, MERLIN, etc.

The evaluation of BioAgora’s dissemination and exploitation efforts confirms that the majority of KPIs set for the period M1-M36 have been successfully achieved, with several targets - such as website traffic, social media engagement, event participation and collaboration with related projects - significantly overperformed. This momentum has prompted a revision and upward adjustment of selected KPI thresholds, reflecting the project’s growing visibility and relevance across stakeholder communities. The KPIs that still haven’t been met, such as the creation of the BioAgora factsheets, are mostly scheduled for the second half of the project’s duration, when dissemination of mature project results is highly necessary. Other KPIs, such as the creation of project policy briefs, are also subject to deliberation on the optimal content type and communication approach, with the achieving of this KPI also to be met by the end of the project’s duration. The evaluation of the progress has also shown that the project newsletter which has gained a considerable amount of subscribers can be optimised and a further emphasis to be provided on this communication channel in the next period of the project’s duration.

At the same time, the evaluation underscores the need for a strategic shift in focus. While the initial phase of the project appropriately emphasised broad outreach and parallel strands of activity to establish visibility, the second half demands more integrated, outcome-driven communication. It is now imperative that BioAgora conveys, with clarity and precision, what the project’s aim and final outputs are, why they are valuable and how stakeholders can engage with and benefit from them.

As BioAgora transitions into its final phase, a key priority will be the articulation and adoption of a cohesive set of key messages. These will serve to unify the project's diverse elements and guide target audiences toward the emerging SSBD. This strategic alignment will not only support the successful launch of the Service but will also strengthen BioAgora's long-term contribution to EU biodiversity governance.

Looking ahead, BioAgora will sustain its trajectory of ambitious communication while placing greater emphasis on targeted, policy-relevant messaging. The objective is to ensure that all engagement activities reinforce the project's legacy, support institutional uptake, and maximise the long-term impact of the SSBD.

1.2. Objectives of the DEC actions for M36-M60

SECTION SUMMARY

Based on the evaluation of the progress and the overall timeframe of the project, a specific set of objectives for DEC action for M36-M60 is presented in this section.

Building on the framework established in D7.1 and MS7.1 as well as the evaluation of performance presented in this deliverable (*see Section 1.1*), project objectives have been refined to support the evolving needs of the project and ensure alignment with its central mission: the development and uptake of the SSBD. As BioAgora moves into its final implementation phase, DEC activities are increasingly focused on supporting the visibility, usability, and sustainability of the project's main outcome – the SSBD.

The overarching aim is to ensure broad awareness, effective engagement and meaningful uptake of the tools, methods and networks developed under BioAgora while creating the conditions for the long-term exploitation and institutionalisation of project results.

The specific objectives for the remaining time of the project are:

1. Promote the uptake of BioAgora outputs and tools.

- a. Disseminate factsheets, infographics, videos, policy-related documents, research articles and other outputs in formats tailored to audience needs.
- b. Facilitate the use of Knowledge Exchange Network methodologies, SPSI tools and assessment processes across relevant sectors.
- c. Integrate selected outputs into the Science Service's content library and communication channels.

2. Maximise exploitation potential and sustainability of KERs.

- a. Communicate the long-term benefits of the Science Service as a strategic tool of the biodiversity SPSI.
- b. Involve key institutional actors (e.g. EC services, the KCBD, National Focal Points) in planning for post-project continuity.
- c. Align exploitation planning with the Science Service business model and legacy strategy (developed in coordination with WP4).

3. Support stakeholder engagement and community-building.

- a. Strengthen participation in the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora and Knowledge Exchange Networks as a foundation for the Science Service.

- b. Provide tailored entry points for researchers, policy-makers, civil society and business to engage in co-creation processes.
- c. Foster collaborations with Horizon Europe projects, networks and platforms to amplify impact.

4. Position BioAgora within the EU biodiversity knowledge landscape.

- a. Consolidate BioAgora’s reputation as a trusted, high-level initiative contributing to EU biodiversity governance.
- b. Reinforce links with the KCBD and policy missions of the European Green Deal.
- c. Participate in relevant clustering activities, campaigns (e.g. #TransformativeChange4Biodiversity campaign) and EU-wide consultations.

5. Ensure stakeholder preparedness for the SSBD pilot launch.

- a. Further raise awareness of the SSBD’s purpose, structure and added value among target groups.
- b. Build anticipation for the Autumn 2026 launch through targeted campaigns, events, and promotional materials.
- c. Equip stakeholders with practical information about how to contribute to and benefit from the SSBD.

These objectives will be implemented through a coordinated set of activities outlined in Sections 3 (Updated Engagement Strategy) and 4 (Implementation Plan for M36-M60), with dedicated actions tailored to each stakeholder subgroup.

2. Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Tools, Target Groups, and Key Messages

This section outlines the strategic tools, channels and target groups that BioAgora’s DEC activities address throughout the project. Based on the information developed and presented in the initial PDEC (D7.1), a refinement of the key elements and messages tailored to for BioAgora's aim and target groups is provided below, to ensure consistent, impactful, and audience-specific engagement.

2.1. Tools and Channels

SECTION SUMMARY

This section provides an overview of the BioAgora communication and dissemination channels through which the DEC actions and initiatives are shared with the relevant target groups. A table of tools and channels is provided. Newly introduced channels are marked in colour on the summary table.

BioAgora utilises a set of communication tools and channels to engage its key target groups, support knowledge dissemination and increase the visibility of the SSBD. The selection and deployment of tools are guided by the

evolving communication objectives of the project - from awareness-raising in the early stages to stakeholder engagement, knowledge integration and institutional visibility in the lead-up to the SSBD pilot launch.

The performance of tools and channels is continuously tracked via KPIs and feedback loops. The evaluation of BioAgora DEC actions, tools and channels is provided in Section 1.1 of the present document. BioAgora adapts its communication mix and messaging based on insights and evolving stakeholder needs, ensuring strategic alignment with the development of the SSBD and policy relevance.

The set of tools and channels that BioAgora will use in the period M36-M60 are based on the tools and channels list provided in the initial PDEC (D7.1). A list of updated tools and channels based on evaluation of effectiveness and the evolving needs of the project is provided below (Table 2, please note that the new tools are marked with different colour). The target groups are presented in more details in Section 2.2 below. KPIs associated with tools and channels are indicated in Section 4 (Implementation plan).

Table 2: Tools and channels for DEC actions and target group engagement (updated)

Tool	Target groups	Purpose/Description
Main Digital Communication Tools and Channels		
Project Website	All	Main hub for updates, deliverables, tools, and stakeholder sections
SSBD Webplatform (in development)	All	Interface for facilitation of the Science Service's functions, including answering requests and stakeholder interaction
KCBD Integration (planned)	EC	Long-term sustainability through EU knowledge infrastructure
Social Media - LinkedIn	All	Institutional engagement and professional visibility
Social Media - Bluesky*	All	real-time updates, policy news, and campaign outreach
Social Media - YouTube	All	hosting explanatory videos, interviews and outreach campaigns
<i>*Bluesky was introduced to the project communication channels in January 2025, substituting X/Twitter.</i>		
Publication Tools		
Project Newsletter	All	triannual updates featuring partner stories, outputs and upcoming events
Knowledge Agora Newsletter	Knowledge Providers	a new communication tool that will aim to support the growing community of BioAgora knowledge contributors constituting the larger networks of the project and the Science Service (it is foreseen to take turns with the tri-annual BioAgora general newsletter) and to focus

Tool	Target groups	Purpose/Description
		on SSBD developments)
Press Releases	Interest Groups	Synthesised presentation of project output for wide-spread media outreach
Factsheets & Infographics	All (depending on factsheet content)	Simplified, visual summaries of project themes, highlights and findings
Deliverables & Reports	All	Communication campaigns on deliverables and reports
Templates, Guidelines and Stories for Enhancing Outreach Dedicated Compilations of Communication Materials	All (depending on content)	template collections aiming to provide a communications toolkit for relevant stakeholders, thus amplifying BioAgora’s outreach through the utilisation of partner organisations’ communication platforms
SSBD Visual Toolkit	All	the visual toolkit of the SSBD as a main instrument for showcasing the functionalities of the platform, also providing an informative walkthrough instrument for users
Digital Dashboard	All	a digital dashboard aiming to provide support to the SSBD and its functions as well as a well-structured information for the engagement possibilities with BioAgora
Videos	All (depending on content)	<p>Videos to be produced on a number of occasions until the end of the project</p> <p>Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an animated video on the SSBD • testimonial short videos provided by targeted projects and initiatives for the launch of the SSBD <p>interviews and webinars on the project’s video sharing channels for maximum visibility.</p>
Outreach Formats and Events		
BioAgora-Organised Events	All (depending on content)	Workshops, trainings, SSBD co-design dialogues
Conference Attendance	Knowledge Providers and Users	Strategic visibility at high-level EU and global events

Tool	Target groups	Purpose/Description
Joint Events with Other Projects and Organisations	All (depending on content)	Joint thematic outreach with related projects
Webinars	All (depending on content)	Delivery of three webinars on the SSBD, providing more information to relevant target groups on its functions and functionalities
Presentation of BioAgora through Promotional Materials at Conferences and Events	All (depending on content)	Project materials for various suitable conferences and events for greater visibility of BioAgora and its main objectives
Joint Communications Campaigns with Relevant Organisations / Projects / Initiatives	Knowledge Providers; Interest Groups	Joint communications campaigns on BioAgora-relevant topics
Collaborative Channels and Partner DEC tools		
Stakeholder Mailing Lists	Knowledge Providers	Segmented updates and invitations
Institutional Briefings	Knowledge Users	Direct outreach to EC services and partner organisations
Joint Promotional Materials	All (depending on content)	Jointly created promotional materials promoting the synergies and the individual outputs by BioAgora and partner projects and initiatives
Shared Communications Calendars and Coordination of Posting	Knowledge Providers, Interest Groups	A calendar will aim to enhance the visibility and interactions between the different biodiversity SPSI organisations and communities that BioAgora is a part of
<p><i>*Tools and channels marked in light blue are new tools and channels that have not been presented in the initial Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (D.7.1).</i></p>		

In the second half of the project, the continued refinement and strategic use of BioAgora's communication tools and channels will be essential to ensuring visibility, relevance, and engagement with the SSBD. The updated set of tools reflects a shift from general outreach to targeted, content-driven engagement aligned with stakeholder priorities and policy timelines. By maintaining a dynamic and adaptive approach, BioAgora ensures that its communication infrastructure not only supports the development and uptake of the SSBD but also aims to ensure the smooth transition from the BioAgora communications infrastructure to the SSBD's permanent communications infrastructure.

2.2. Assessment and update of BioAgora target groups

Section Summary

This section presents an updated classification of BioAgora’s target groups, maintaining the original three categories established in D7.1. (knowledge providers, knowledge users, and interest groups) while also refining and expanding them into tailored subgroups. The revision integrates insights from across the project WPs and Taskforces (most notably drawing insight from D2.1 and T3.4, and the work done within the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora Taskforce) to support more strategic, targeted engagement aligned with the development of the SSBD. A further refinement to the target groups to incorporate the specific role of knowledge-brokering mechanisms is provided.

As outlined in the initial PDEC of BioAgora, the identified target groups are grouped in three larger categories, namely “**knowledge providers**”, “**knowledge users**”, and “**interest groups**”.

This categorisation was further refined to enhance precision and ensure more tailored engagement. In the table below, the original three main stakeholder categories are maintained and have been expanded to include **additional subgroups** that reflect the evolving needs and engagement dynamics of the project. This refinement supports a more strategic and nuanced approach to outreach and collaboration.

A more prominent outline of knowledge-brokering mechanisms is also tailored within the refinement of the target groups, with the aim to ensure a more efficient representation of the variation in terms of engagement pathways of these particular type of stakeholders. The refined target groups are presented in the update target groups graph below (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Refined target group categories of BioAgora

This updated classification draws not only from the communication and engagement priorities outlined in D7.1 but also integrates insights from analyses conducted across other BioAgora work packages, particularly those focused on stakeholder mapping, knowledge needs and SPSI dynamics. The result is a more precise and operational framework that supports targeted engagement and aligns with the development of the SSBD. The updated categorisation of BioAgora stakeholders is provided in Table 3 (below), and it draws the listed organisations representing the target groups from a variety of sources, including BioAgora’s D2.1, the work performed in T3.4 and within WP4, as well as from the detailed categorisation of BioAgora stakeholders done within the work of the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora Taskforce. The target group organisations were further streamlined with the EUBP.

Table 3: Refined target groups of BioAgora

Stakeholder category	Target group	Subgroup	Organisations
Knowledge Providers	T1: Scientific Community	researchers in natural sciences focused on biodiversity research	BioAgora addresses researchers from various levels in order to promote the SSBD and their engagement with its functions. This involves communicating BioAgora messages to different types of researchers, including early-career researchers and freelance researchers.
Knowledge providers	T1: Scientific community	researchers in social sciences focused on biodiversity research	BioAgora addresses researchers from various levels in order to promote the SSBD and their engagement with its functions. This involves communicating BioAgora messages to different types of researchers, including early-career researchers and freelance researchers.
Knowledge Providers	T1: Scientific Community	universities, national academies of sciences and research agencies	Research institutions that advance biodiversity research across local, national and international levels, encompassing both natural and social science perspectives.
Knowledge Providers	T1: Scientific Community	European research networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversa+ • GBIF • Science Europe • Altnet • PEER <i>*This list provides an initial example, as more such networks will be identified through interaction through KENs.</i>
Knowledge Providers	T1: Scientific Community	EU-funded research projects	A list of active EU-funded projects is available in WP3.
Knowledge Providers	T1: Scientific Community	data-sharing platforms and citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity Information System for Europe (BISE)

Stakeholder category	Target group	Subgroup	Organisations
		initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest Information System for Europe (FISE) • Water Information System for Europe (WISE) • GBIF • ECSA • SPOTTERON
Knowledge Providers	T4: SPSI Platforms *This subcategory derives from analysis performed within T3.4, with the extensive information to be provided within T3.4	knowledge synthesis mechanisms: science-driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oppla • Eklipse • Biodiversa+ • Scientific Advice Mechanism • CEE • DGDEAPP at INRAE • Cochrane Collaboration • CASCADE • AGILE • Geneva Science-Policy Interface • The Montpellier Process <p><i>*A more detailed list of organisations representing this target subgroup will be made available in the future deliverable of T3.4</i></p>
Knowledge Providers	T4: SPSI Platforms	global intergovernmental initiatives linking science and policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IPBES • UNEP • UN CBD • GBIF
Knowledge Providers	T4: SPSI Platforms	research infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LifeWatch ERIC • eLTER RI • DiSSCo RI • AnaEE Europe
Knowledge Providers	T4: SPSI Platforms	EUBP observers	EUBP observers official list
Knowledge Providers	T4: SPSI Platforms	strategic platforms (e.g. Future Earth, GEOBON)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future Earth • GEOBON • ESP • Capitals Coalition
Knowledge Providers	T4: SPSI Platforms	think tanks and para-research organisations	Institute for European Environmental Policy (IEEP)
Knowledge Users	T2: EC Directorate-Generals (DGs) & Agencies	core DGs of the EC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DG ENV • DG RTD • DG CLIMA • DG AGRI • DG MARE • DG GROW

Stakeholder category	Target group	Subgroup	Organisations
Knowledge Users	T2: EC DGs & Agencies	JRC and the KCBD	Not applicable
Knowledge Users	T2: EC DGs & Agencies	relevant EU Missions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mission Ocean • Mission Soils
Knowledge Users	T3: European-Level Policy-Makers	Nature Directors and EU Biodiversity Platform (EUBP)	Not applicable
Knowledge Users	T8: Funding Authorities	executive agencies which govern the funding of research and innovation, administering funding provision for knowledge holders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CINEA • LIFE programme • Horizon Europe
Interest Groups	T5: Environmental NGOs	EU-level organisations and European branches of organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WWF European Policy Office • Wetlands International Europe • CEEweb for Biodiversity Greenpeace • BirdLife Europe and Central Asia • IUCN • ICLEI • members of the EU Habitats Forum • European Redlist • European Environmental Bureau • Society for Ecological Restoration - European Chapter • Eurosite • Butterfly Conservation Europe (BCE) • ClientEarth • Coalition Clean Baltic (CCB) • EuroNatur - Stiftung Europäisches Naturerbe (EuroNatur) • Friends of the Earth Europe (FoEE) • Mediterranean Protected Areas Network (MedPAN) • OCEANA • POLLINIS FRANCE (POLLINIS) • Saami Council Headquarters (Saami Council) • Slow Food (NA) • Stichting Rewilding Europe • THE NATURE CONSERVANCY IN EUROPE • TNCE • WCS EU • Wetlands International - European Association (WI-EA) • Whale and Dolphin Conservation (WDC) • WindEurope; World Green Infrastructure Network (WGIN)

Stakeholder category	Target group	Subgroup	Organisations
Interest Groups	T5: Environmental NGOs	global-level organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WWF International • Greenpeace International • BirdLife International • Wetlands International • IUCN • ICLEI • Women4Biodiversity
Interest Groups	T6: Business/ Sectoral Organisations and Private Interest Groups	Business networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BusinessEurope • EU Business @ Biodiversity Platform • Community of European Railway and Infrastructure Companies (CER) • Eurelectric • European Aggregates Association (UEPG)
Interest Groups	T6: Business & Sectoral Organisations	sector-specific platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confédération Européenne des Propriétaires Forestiers (CEPF) • European Landowners' Organization (ELO) • NSF • European Association of Mining Industries, Metal Ores & Industrial Minerals • Federation of Associations for Hunting & Conservation of the EU (FACE) • Freshfel Europe - the forum for the European fresh fruits and vegetables chain • Union Européenne du Commerce du Bétail et des Métiers de la Viande (U.E.C.B.V.) • International Association of Oil & Gas Producers Europe (IOGP Europe) • International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements EU Regional Group (IFOAM EU Group)
Interest Groups	T7: Media	EU-focused media outlets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Euractiv • Politico • Euronews

While the three overarching categories of target groups remain consistent with those defined in D7.1, the classification has been refined through the addition of several strategically relevant subgroups, the specification of existing ones, and the identification of key organisations with which enhanced collaboration should be pursued.

A detailed **engagement strategy for each subgroup** is provided in **Section 3 of the present document**, where specific actions, tools and expected outcomes are outlined.

2.3. Strategic key messages and BioAgora “narrative”

SECTION SUMMARY

This section presents a list of tailored key messages of BioAgora which aim to ensure the efficient proliferation of the project’s messages and the overall Science Service narrative in the phase of its development. An update of the key messages is due with D7.3 which will focus on providing a communications strategy for the Science Service upon its launch.

To ensure the efficient dissemination of BioAgora actions and messages, a set of key messages comprising the BioAgora narrative was developed in D7.1. A necessary update and additional nuancing of the BioAgora key messages are further developed and presented here. These messages adhere to one or more of the key target groups and aim to build the bridge for an efficient long-term cooperation with these target groups.

They are intended to be **audience-sensitive**, with flexibility to evolve over the course of the project. Later iterations (in MS7.1 and the current deliverable) build upon these foundational narratives by incorporating more targeted messages and calls to action (e.g. for scientists, policy-makers, media and civil society).

Based on the evolution of BioAgora’s communication strategy from D7.1 to the final phase as well as the incorporation of the messaging priorities emerging from MS7.1 and the current strategic positioning, what follows is a **comprehensive and audience-sensitive set of core key messages** for the **final phase of the BioAgora project** as well as and the upcoming **Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD)**, a deliverable for which is due in M60 (D7.3).

These messages are designed to align with the **refined target audience categories** and to support the final outreach and engagement activities of the project.

The five key messages outlined for the period M39 - M60 are as follows:

1. *BioAgora mobilises knowledge to support evidence-informed decision-making across EU biodiversity-related policy processes and across different Directorates-General.*
2. *BioAgora engages a diverse set of actors, especially in answering knowledge requests from the European Commission, thus shaping an inclusive Science-Policy-Society Interface for biodiversity.*
3. *BioAgora engages with a vibrant community through Knowledge Exchange Networks which form the foundation of the Science Service for Biodiversity.*
4. *BioAgora builds the Science Service for Biodiversity in close collaboration with the Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity and other Units of the European Commission.*
5. *BioAgora invites you to take part in developing the Science Service by answering requests, co-organising events and joining the Science Service network.*

The five key messages listed above adhere to the BioAgora target groups, with some of them being particularly relevant to specific target groups, which are presented in Figure 2 (below).

Figure 2: Key messages relevant to target groups

A further update of the BioAgora key messages is envisioned in relation to the upcoming promotion strategy for the Science Service for Biodiversity (D7.3).

The updated categorisation of BioAgora’s target groups, the outlining of the project’s key messages, and the introduction of new tools and channels for DEC provide a more nuanced and operational foundation for strategic engagement during the project’s final phase. By expanding and specifying key subgroups, as well as taking into account the work done within BioAgora WP2 and WP3, this updated framework ensures that the DEC efforts are effectively aligned with stakeholder needs, expectations and roles. It also supports the co-development and future uptake of the SSBD by positioning each stakeholder group within a clearer value proposition and engagement pathway. The updated BioAgora target group categorisation also allowed the generation of a shortlist of priority organisations and types of organisations for which a more comprehensive engagement strategy was developed (provided in Section 3.2 below). The updated classification and engagement strategy will directly inform the tailored engagement actions in M36-M60 of the duration of the project (Section 3.1).

3. Updated Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy

Based on the evaluation of the DEC actions and results in M1-M8, and with having in mind the strategic objectives of BioAgora until the end of the project’s duration, a detailed update of the DEC strategy of the project is provided in this Section. The strategy is structured in accordance with the three main categories of target groups (outlined and revised in the previous section). Also, a concise practical strategy for DEC engagement with key actors and target group subcategories is provided in Section 3.2.

A central objective of BioAgora is to deliver results that are not only robust, but also accessible, actionable, and sustainable for a broad spectrum of users across the EU biodiversity SPSI. As the project enters its final phase, the

dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy places particular emphasis on a set of foundational Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that are instrumental to the development and operationalisation of the Science Service and its contribution to the KCBD. These strategically prioritised KERs form the backbone of the current PDEC action roadmap and are positioned to maximise institutional impact, uptake, and long-term sustainability. While these KERs represent the core focus of engagement at this stage, the strategy remains inclusive and adaptive - ensuring that other relevant project outputs and emerging results are also disseminated and promoted in alignment with stakeholder needs and project evolution.

The KERs prioritised in this strategic phase include:

- The Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD) - the principal interface linking scientific knowledge with EU biodiversity policymaking, including a structured answering requests mechanism.
- The Biodiversity Knowledge Agora and the Knowledge Exchange Networks (KENs) - a growing community of expert networks that underpin thematic dialogue and feed into the SSBD.
- SPSI knowledge, tools, and methodologies - practical instruments for knowledge synthesis and stakeholder engagement, including workshops, databases, and participatory frameworks.

The following section elaborates on each of these areas and their respective roles in supporting the final implementation and long-term legacy of BioAgora.

The refinement of BioAgora's target groups provides the basis for a more strategic tailored engagement approach towards the various target groups that recognises the diversity of their roles, motivations and modes of participation in the processes developed for the SSBD. As the project moves toward the launch of the SSBD in the end of 2026, engagement actions shift from general awareness-raising to more target-driven involvement, tailored to each group's capacity to contribute to and benefit from the SSBD.

3.1. General DEC engagement strategy (per target group)

SECTION SUMMARY

Each subsection that follows outlines tailored approaches to engage these categories effectively, ensuring that communication efforts are aligned with the specific roles, expectations and contributions of each group in the development and uptake of the SSBD. The strategies reflect both the evolving engagement needs identified throughout the project implementation and the refined stakeholder typology established in collaboration with other BioAgora work packages.

The overall approach to the DEC activities of BioAgora remains within the scope of the EC guidelines for dissemination and exploitation of results, with a core aim to provide access to project results and introduce the opportunities that BioAgora and the SSBD provide to the respective target groups. The variation in the different types of target groups call for a differentiated approach to DEC for each. While the DEC actions directed to knowledge holders and interest groups aim to provide information about the streamlined pathways for engagement with the SSBD developed within the BioAgora project, the actions towards policy-makers mostly constitute close collaboration with the EC in terms of developing the future SSBD and promoting it to relevant DGs and EC Units.

The next period of the project communication and dissemination will see additional elements of stakeholder engagement regarding the target groups being introduced. This is in line with BioAgora's approach for a co-

creation of the SSBD with the EC as well as the necessity for effectively promoting the network of experts which will serve as the knowledge provider backbone of the SSBD.

The detailed strategic communication and dissemination roadmaps for the respective target groups are provided below in Sections 3.1.1., 3.1.2 and 3.1.3.

3.1.1. Strategic Communication and Dissemination Roadmap for Knowledge Providers

This communication and dissemination roadmap outlines how BioAgora will engage knowledge providers - researchers, academic organisations, research networks and data platforms - through targeted, strategic communications to support the development of the SSBD knowledge holder network and the visibility of the SSBD. The goal is to position the SSBD as a credible, relevant and valuable interface for translating scientific knowledge into policy impact while empowering providers to actively contribute to and collaborate with it.

1. PERMANENT VISIBILITY AND POSITIONING (CONTINUED FROM M1, M36-M60)

Objective: Further raise the visibility among knowledge providers of the SSBD's and other BioAgora outcomes' vision, value, and relevance

Actions:

- launch a targeted communication campaign to knowledge providers showcasing the SSBD's development and the opportunities to engage with the SSBD and its functions;
- disseminate an explanatory graphic and a redesign of the dedicated SSBD landing page on the BioAgora website to highlight the benefits for knowledge providers and provide pathways for engagement;
- promote the BioAgora and SSBD developments through partner newsletters, LinkedIn, Bluesky and mailing lists of key research networks (e.g. GBIF, Biodiversa+);
- present the SSBD at major research conferences and EU-funded project meetings;
- submit a BioAgora article on the SSBD to the Science for Environmental Policy newsletter.

2. ENGAGEMENT AND RECRUITMENT (CONTINUED FROM M1, M36-M60)

Objective: Provide further support for the recruiting of researchers and institutions into SSBD development processes and ticket request handling

Actions:

- create online and in-person events aimed at engaging different groups of knowledge providers (e.g. a BioAgora stakeholder event, a targeted webinar for showcasing features of the SSBD, etc.);
- share targeted messages outlining how participation supports policy impact and scientific visibility, develop a special extension to the BioAgora key messages focusing on policy impact of participation in the SSBD and advertise it through social media campaigns, newsletter publications, the project website, news releases, etc.;
- develop a communications toolkit for institutional liaisons to share across their networks;
- launch a tailor-made SSBD animated video explaining the workings of the SSBD (to be included on the SSBD homepage).

3. CREATION OF SSBD AND CONTRIBUTION TO THE SSBD (MONTHS 46-53)

Objective: Promote the SSBD and advertise participation of knowledge holders in the SSBD

Actions:

- promote participation in the SSBD via walkthrough guides, FAQ factsheets and preliminary access to the platform;
- highlight exemplary contributions to the SSBD in newsletters, blogs and social media – e.g. first success story campaign from the active tickets;
- partner with EU projects to co-produce research-to-policy brief or conduct research-to-policy webinar on the topics of active tickets;
- communicate the visibility and citation benefits of contributing to the SSBD.

4. RECOGNITION AND LONG-TERM ENGAGEMENT (M53-60)

Objective: Sustain engagement and establish a long-term communication loop with knowledge providers / Communicate transition from BioAgora to SSBD

Actions:

- launch a 'Why I Joined SSBD' testimonial series featuring voices from academia and research institutions;
- launch a second success stories campaign;
- provide periodic updates on policy impact of contributions through a dedicated dashboard or factsheet;
- launch a digital dashboard;
- ensure a smooth transition from the BioAgora infrastructure to the SSBD infrastructure;
- support the promotion of enrolment in the SSBD through partners' communication and dissemination channels.

3.1.2. Strategic Communications Roadmap for Knowledge Users (EC)

This part of the strategic communications roadmap outlines BioAgora's approach to engaging the EC and the relevant services, including DGs, Executive Agencies and the KCBD. The aim is to ensure that EC stakeholders are well-informed, involved in co-design processes and prepared to integrate and institutionalise the SSBD as a long-term tool for policy support. BioAgora will proceed to apply a structured and phased engagement strategy with the Commission with a focus on institutional alignment as well as communicating and disseminating the development and adoption of the SSBD.

In M36-39, BioAgora will deliver concise SSBD introductory slide decks to key DGs including DG ENV, RTD, AGRI, CLIMA and MARE. This will serve as key support for fostering institutional awareness, helping frame the SSBD within the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the Green Deal context.

From M39-44, a BioAgora factsheet on the SSBD's answering requests function to be created and disseminated to key target groups, incl. EC focal points.

In M46, BioAgora will organise and host an activity around the Science Service at the 2026 EU Green Week (or a related thematic EU Week) in order to promote and amplify the visibility of the SSBD as an efficient tool for supporting biodiversity policymaking.

Between M42-50, BioAgora will host another dedicated lunch event (or similar) with representatives from key DGs other than DG ENV. These dialogues will aim to uncover functional expectations and build shared ownership around the SSBD's design and applications. The focus will thus be on the answering requests function and a preview of the infrastructural elements of the webplatform already available at this point.

During M48-52, a detailed infographic explaining the SSBD functions, including the urgent and in-depth requests will be produced and disseminated to target groups, including Policy-makers. This will be followed with the production and publication of a comprehensive animated video (M48-M52) which will serve as a key tool for explaining the Science Service’s workings and outlining its position within the EU biodiversity SPSI.

Between M48-53, a second BioAgora factsheet to policymakers on the transformative potential of mechanisms such as the one developed within the SSBD will be provided.

From M52-56, BioAgora will develop and present a roadmap for the potential handover or institutional integration of the SSBD.

In M54-58, communication will focus on showcasing evidence of the SSBD’s policy impact (through dashboards, briefings, and narrative case studies), building momentum for its future adoption.

A special consideration will be provided to the DEC activities surrounding the SSBD’s launch event (envisioned to take place in Autumn 2026), with a prelaunch campaign and post-launch dissemination campaign envisioned to achieve efficient coverage and maximum reach. Within the frame of these efforts, a third BioAgora factsheet to policy-makers will be launched as well as a dedicated testimonials campaign which will address all BioAgora target groups.

The final phase of BioAgora’s duration will be dedicated to the support of the growth of the Science Service with dedicated campaigns showcasing the BioAgora Knowledge Exchange Networks and success stories circulating in the last months of the project’s duration.

Upon its completion, BioAgora will provide a detailed legacy booklet which will aim to serve as a useful tool for policymakers in terms of providing good practices and lessons learnt, a walkthrough of the various KERs of the project and an outline of impactful takeaways from the project’s outcomes.

3.1.3. Strategic Communications Roadmap for Interest Groups

This part of the strategic communications roadmap of BioAgora outlines its engagement approach with key interest groups identified in the PDEC, including environmental NGOs, business and sectoral organisations and media subgroups. These actors play a critical role in amplifying the visibility, societal relevance and uptake of the SSBD. At the same time, they also contribute valuable knowledge, advocacy and communication functions to support the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

1. POSITIONING AND VALUE FRAMING: BUILDING COLLABORATION AND TRUST (M36-46)

Objective for positioning: Communicate the purpose and relevance of SSBD to civil society, business and media actors.

Actions:

- launch of an infographic presenting the SSBD and its functions within the larger landscape of biodiversity SPSI;
- create a factsheet on the role of the SSBD and its functions in the biodiversity SPSI;
- submit BioAgora news in NGO newsletters, business forums, and specialist media publications.
- promote the BioAgora narrative on the transformative potential of networks through infographics developed together with BioAgora partners in relation to D2.3;
- initiate working groups or informal dialogues between communicators to explore opportunities for joint content creation (e.g. joint factsheet or infographic).
-

2. CO-CREATION AND CAMPAIGN ENGAGEMENT (M46-52)

Objective: Collaborate on outreach and policy campaigns and enhance content visibility

Actions:

- feature contributors in the dedicated Synergies section of the BioAgora website;
- develop thematic guidelines and/or communications packages around key EU milestones (e.g. Nature Restoration Law, processes of the UN CBD - together with CO-OP4CBD) and disseminate them to relevant interest groups;
- integrate SSBD visibility into high-impact NGO- and business-led communications campaigns (e.g. #NaturePositive, #BiodiversityDay, #Women4Biodiversity).

3. LEGACY AND INSTITUTIONAL AMPLIFICATION (MONTHS 52-60)

Objective: Sustain engagement through structured communication partnerships and encourage interest groups to amplify the SSBD launch

Actions:

- showcase the benefits of the SSBD through the two success story campaigns (described in Section 3.1.1.);
- establish communications cooperation with organisations to continue post-project advocacy and visibility.

3.2. Key Stakeholders DEC Engagement Strategy

To support the effective uptake and long-term visibility of the SSBD, BioAgora has developed a targeted strategic communication approach for key stakeholders. These stakeholders were identified through a prioritisation process led under Action 5 of the Taskforce Knowledge Agora, which brought together insights from stakeholder mapping, engagement outputs and work conducted under multiple BioAgora work packages. The resulting prioritisation database supports a more focused, operational framework for collaboration and communication with institutions that play a critical role in the SPSI. The list of prioritised stakeholders includes prominent organisations across the science-policy landscape, such as Biodiversa+, Eklipse, the European Environment Agency (EEA), IPBES, eLTER, IUCN, ESP, WWF Europe and BirdLife International. These institutions exemplify the breadth of BioAgora's engagement - ranging from EU-level policy support bodies to science-policy platforms, research infrastructures and influential civil society actors.

Tailored communication with key actors ensures the efficient proliferation of the SSBD and enhances BioAgora's positioning within the European biodiversity science-policy landscape. By aligning messaging, visibility and co-branding opportunities with these stakeholders, BioAgora increases relevance, trust and shared ownership across the ecosystem of knowledge providers, users and intermediaries.

Rather than listing stakeholders individually, a set of concrete communication actions is proposed below. These actions are applicable across institutions identified as priorities and serve as a baseline for bilateral or network-based cooperation:

1. JOINT VISIBILITY AND KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE

- Feature stakeholder contributions in the Synergies section of the BioAgora website.
- Exchange web content and promote mutual visibility through dedicated subpages or updates, and exchange of newsletter updates.
- Co-organise and co-promote high-visibility events and webinars.

2. CO-AUTHORED AND JOINT MATERIALS

- Develop factsheets, blog posts and explainer videos highlighting shared initiatives or overlapping thematic areas.
- Invite stakeholders to co-author policy communication content and opinion pieces on BioAgora channels.

3. TESTIMONIAL AND CAMPAIGN PARTICIPATION

- Involve key stakeholders in the SSBD testimonial series (in video or written form).
- Collaborate on joint campaigns (e.g. International Day of Biodiversity, Restoration Days, SPI awareness).

4. NEWSLETTER AND SOCIAL MEDIA SYNERGIES

- Cross-promote content in newsletters and social media, aligning editorial calendars for shared moments.
- Contribute updates to each other's stakeholder networks.

5. TECHNICAL AND THEMATIC ALIGNMENT

- Coordinate communications around SSBD use cases and Knowledge Exchange Network activities.
- Highlight stakeholder data, practices or success stories relevant to SSBD development.

6. OPEN AND EVOLVING COLLABORATION

- Maintain flexibility to deepen collaboration where strategic, structural communications partnerships are mutually beneficial.
- Extend this approach to additional organisations as engagement needs evolve.

Two dialogues for communication synchronisation that have already begun with Eklipse and with Biodiversa+. Biodiversa+ is a key strategic partner for BioAgora due to its central role in coordinating European biodiversity research and supporting science-policy integration at the EU level. The collaboration aims to reinforce the collective visibility of both initiatives and advance the uptake of science into biodiversity governance, being comprised of the following actions:

- propose the development of a co-branded newsletter (not periodic) and the exchange of web content (BioAgora to feature Biodiversa+ information on its website and Biodiversa+ to highlight contributions to SSBD on their website);
- feature Biodiversa+ case studies and funded project results across BioAgora's social media channels and newsletter;
- coordinate communication timelines for joint event promotion, SSBD updates and Biodiversa+ key initiatives;
- invite Biodiversa+ to contribute to a dedicated SSBD stakeholder testimonial video;
- create and grow the SPSI Communications Hub together.

Tailored individual communication synergies are also envisioned by BioAgora and other knowledge-brokering mechanisms such as Eklipse, with which BioAgora is already in close cooperation in terms of both answering requests and exchange of communication information. In terms of synchronising communications efforts with Eklipse, the progress towards this has been natural in terms of the fact that Eklipse handles requests as well. In this relation, a synchronisation of newsletters (creation of dedicated permanent sections), periodic updates about developments and current calls for knowledge or calls for experts.

More specific is the place of IPBES in the context of the EU SPSI. Being an intergovernmental organisation operating on the global scale, IPBES is a crucial communications stakeholder for BioAgora which defines the global biodiversity narrative in general and thus influences the EU biodiversity communications narrative. For this

reason, BioAgora envisions to cooperate with IPBES in the following ways, taking into account the specifics of the communications processes of the organisation:

- share news and results via IPBES-related mailing lists and newsletters (O-Net stakeholder communication channel);
- develop a thematic BioAgora publications series on key IPBES outputs, plenaries and assessments (in cooperation with RESPIN);
- participate in joint communications campaigns led by IPBES or other partners from the larger network of the UN CBD.

This unified strategy ensures consistency in BioAgora's external positioning, leverages the networks of established actors and supports the long-term institutionalisation of the SSBD across the European SPSI.

3.2.1. Engagement strategy towards EU-funded research projects

BioAgora recognises the essential role of EU-funded research projects in shaping and informing biodiversity science and policy in Europe. As such, a dedicated strand of the project's DEC strategy is focused on strengthening engagement with this stakeholder group. The objective is to ensure a two-way exchange: promoting the uptake of BioAgora's key messages and services among these projects, while also facilitating the integration of their knowledge and expertise into the Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD).

The strategy involves several key pillars. First, BioAgora will proactively communicate its overarching narrative and core key messages to EU-funded projects, ensuring that these projects are fully aware of BioAgora's objectives, contributions to the science-policy-society interface, and opportunities for collaboration. Second, specific information about pathways for engagement will be disseminated through targeted outreach - highlighting how research projects can contribute to, benefit from, and actively shape the SSBD, particularly through the answering requests mechanism and Knowledge Exchange Networks.

Third, BioAgora will continue to pursue joint communication and dissemination activities with EU-funded projects, including co-organised events, collaborative campaigns, and cross-promotion through digital channels. The DEC methods already developed for priority stakeholders - including content exchange, testimonial participation, joint visibility efforts, and aligned editorial calendars - will also be applied to cooperation with EU-funded research projects.

This approach is not new to BioAgora but builds on successful foundations. EU-funded projects have already been involved across multiple BioAgora activities, particularly within the Knowledge Exchange Networks, the Transformative Change Cluster, and the marine biodiversity cluster. With the further development of the Knowledge Exchange Networks and the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora network, these collaborative relationships are expected to deepen, offering structured platforms for continued cooperation and visibility.

In terms of synergies, BioAgora has already established effective working relationships with projects such as CO-OP4CBD and RESPIN, including the organisation of joint events for the 2024 Convention on Biological Diversity COP16, the Alternet conference in May 2025, and the creation of a shared communications calendar. These synergies will be further strengthened in the upcoming period, reinforcing BioAgora's role as a hub for research-policy integration and as a catalyst for coordinated communication across the European biodiversity research landscape.

4. Implementation Plan for DEC activities (2025 - 2027)

As laid out above, the three years of BioAgora’s implementation already elapsed have been underpinned by practical circumstances and realities that could not have been accounted for in the initial PDEC laid out in D7.1. With the refinement of key messages, outreach approaches and stakeholder groups of interest at the core of this update, a reevaluation of aims and methods is necessarily in order for the remaining 24 months of the project. This is further mandated by the launch of both the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora and the SSBD, the KERs underpinning BioAgora’s vision, that are foreseen for this time.

Therefore, the WP7-relevant KPI benchmarks for the period between July 2025 and June 2027 have been adjusted in recognition of the consortium’s improved understanding of target groups and outreach practices. This information has been summarised in Table 6 with a succinct showcase of the foundational DEC activity types along with their intended audiences and objectives.

Table 6: Implementation plan for M36-M60

Tool	Target group	Action in M36-M60	Target for M36-M60
BioAgora website	All	<p>Large-scale update of the website to ensure the alliance of the website with core elements of the Science Service process</p> <p>Develop a special landing page for Knowledge Exchange Networks to facilitate their development and the later transfer to the webplatform</p> <p>Further develop the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora section of the website to structure and facilitate the needs of the growing community</p>	<p>3000 users</p> <p>> 50 countries</p>
Social media: LinkedIn, BlueSky, YouTube	All	Create more synergies on social media with other key stakeholders (a particular focus on creating a set of communication clusters, such as the TCC)	total number of followers by M60: 1500 (LinkedIn), 300 (BlueSky)

Tool	Target group	Action in M36-M60	Target for M36-M60
Promotional materials	All	Create new promotional materials - brochures, factsheets, stickers, smaller brochures (A6) Improve download rate from the website	<u>150 downloads/item</u> <u>50 distributed/per event</u>
BioAgora newsletter	All	Create a new newsletter for the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora and Knowledge Exchange Networks stakeholders Continue following best practices for all newsletter editions	3 general newsletters for the period M36-M60 3 Agora/Networks newsletters for the period M36-M60 an additional 5-10% increase in total subscribers
Press relations and media coverage	TG3	Issue press release about the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora to increase the visibility of the newly launched network	2 press releases
Policy brief	TG2	Issue one policy brief targeted at EC policy-makers to showcase the benefits of the SSBD and this approach to integrate expert knowledge in political decision-making as a whole (scheduled for M50-M60)	1 policy brief
Videos	All	Create a BioAgora SSBD animated video (to be produced in M40-M50 and featured on the SSBD frontpage)	1 video 300 views on YouTube
Events (organised)	All	Continue organising events aiming to promote the functions of the SSBD (e.g. stakeholder event) Organise the launch event of the SSBD with a high impact on visibility and outreach via	2 events

Tool	Target group	Action in M36-M60	Target for M36-M60
		a tailored dissemination campaign	
EC lunch event	TG2	Facilitate another specially organised lunch event with EC colleagues until the end of the project's duration	1 event
Webinars	TG1&3	Organise 3 webinars directed at the different target groups and subgroups of the project	3 webinars 100+ attendees (total)
Conferences	All	Participate in different conferences and forums, at which it will present the output of the project and the functions of the SSBD	15 conferences
Factsheets	All	Issue 5 factsheets on the SSBD directed at different target groups and subgroups. Issue 5 factsheets on various BioAgora-derived topics (how to engage with BioAgora for Horizon Europe Calls; the transformative potential of networks factsheet; Knowledge Exchange Network factsheets)	10 factsheets
Infographics	All	Create a final SSBD infographic to be used for DEC activities across different target groups	1 infographic
Joint actions with other projects	All	Deepen the synergies with other projects like CO-OP4CBD and RESPSIN	2 events per year
Testimonials	All	Compile testimonials by key knowledge providers, knowledge brokers, academic organisations, networks, etc.	5 testimonials

Tool	Target group	Action in M36-M60	Target for M36-M60
Communications toolkit for institutional liasons (incl. specially designed slide deck for policy-makers)	TG2	Produce a toolkit for target group 2 with elements relating to the other target groups where appropriate and relevant	1 toolkit
Success stories	All	Put together a success stories campaign before the official launch of the SSBD (to be concluded towards the end of the project)	2 campaigns

The implementation of BioAgora’s DEC activities is grounded in a target group-responsive strategy that aligns with the project’s overarching goal, namely the successful development, visibility and institutional integration of the SSBD. Through the strategic use of targeted tools, coordinated timelines and bilateral engagement pathways BioAgora aims to ensure that its key messages reach the right audiences at the right time through impactful channels. The implementation roadmap not only supports immediate project objectives but also lays the foundation for the long-term uptake and sustainability of the SSBD.

5. Conclusions

Being a key update of the DEC strategy of BioAgora, this deliverable accounts not only for the period leading up to the project’s conclusion in 2027, but also sets the background for what comes after the finalisation of the project. At its core, the SSBD’s success as a focal point of Europe’s biodiversity governance landscape will hinge on the legacy planning and sustainability provisions BioAgora will develop in pursuit of the Science Service’s integration into the KCBD. Bearing this in mind, D7.4 has pursued three primary objectives:

- comparatively and critically taking stock of past and current communication and dissemination achievements;
- identifying how DEC efforts may be improved and enhanced to encompass the project DEC activities towards providing a robust foundation for the SSBD’s long-term narrative;
- setting out a performance standard supporting the SSBD’s successful launch and long-term longevity.

In relation to the first of these objectives, it can be concluded that BioAgora has succeeded in achieving most of its outreach targets for the initial phase of the project. Communication efforts aimed at raising awareness of the project’s purpose and progress, as well as the dissemination of its results to relevant stakeholders, have been implemented in alignment with the established benchmarks. This is evidenced in Table 1 of the present deliverable, which compares intended outcomes with actual achievements - demonstrating that, in several instances, performance has exceeded expectations. Where challenges in performance were identified through the evaluation process, they have been acknowledged and addressed through targeted measures.

This deliverable provides a crucial reevaluation and refinement of BioAgora key messages, target groups, and DEC activities, thus providing an opportunity to:

- structure and reformulate the project’s key messages in favour of succinct, impactful and targeted wording;

- further the categorisation of the stakeholder groups and subgroups first identified in D7.1 so as to achieve a degree of categorical distinctiveness that encompasses the extant variety in the biodiversity SPSI landscape;
- adopt a more tailored DEC engagement roadmap that assigns concrete timelines and methodologies in approaching specific end users and interested parties, thus providing instruments for further increasing outreach and impact across target groups.

On the basis of all conclusions reached thus far and the reactions they have necessitated, the document also anticipates and addresses future trajectories, challenges and prospects inherent within and beyond the implementation period. As in previous instances, the consortium retains its ambitious outlook in terms of setting KPI benchmarks exceeding what has been previously envisioned.

The next period for BioAgora DEC activities will encompass the need for the development of a tailored promotion strategy for the Science Service for Biodiversity (D7.3), looking to launch the SSBD in the designated timeframe and through collaboration and complementarity with the KCBD. Autumn 2026 will see the submission of a dedicated promotion strategy being developed for the roll-out and long-term development of the SSBD as part of D7.3 Promotion strategy of the Science Service, where a tailored approach to the long-term communication of the Science Service as a long-term science-policy interface mechanism will be provided.

Naturally, this will be accompanied by an intensive and comprehensive DEC activity package that harnesses all outreach channels and networks established and developed throughout the project. As outlined in this deliverable, the upcoming period within BioAgora is going to be dedicated to the further expansion of the project's outreach activities, notably focusing on a more structured engagement in DEC activities with key stakeholders.

With the development and finalisation of the Science Service's core components, including its governance model and business plan, as well as the launch of the webplatform, the DEC activities will further align with the SSBD infrastructure to ensure the efficient transition from the project to the permanent entity (the SSBD).

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Annexes

ANNEX 1: MS7.1 UPDATED PLAN FOR EXPLOITATION AND DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS

Bio Knowledge Agora: Developing the Science Service for
European Research and Biodiversity Policymaking

MS7.1. Update of the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

28/06/2024

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Pensoft Publishers

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
SSBD	Science Service for Biodiversity
CDE	Communication, dissemination, and exploitation
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RP	Reporting Period

BACKGROUND: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF BIOAGORA RESULTS

BioAgora is a collaborative project funded by the Horizon Europe programme. It aims to connect research results on biodiversity to the needs of policy making in a targeted dialogue between scientists, other knowledge holders and policy actors. Its main outcome will be the development of a Science Service for Biodiversity. This new service will fully support the ecological transition required by the European Green Deal and the European Union’s Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

To maximise the impact of the project’s outputs, a detailed Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of BioAgora results was developed in M6 (D7.1. Initial Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results). The initial PDEC developed a detailed strategy for the outreach of project results, with relevant target groups identified, as well as the appropriate tools for engaging these stakeholder groups.

The current document represents a planned update of the initial PDEC, aiming to fine tune the project’s communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) actions for the upcoming project period M24-M36.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a milestone of the BioAgora project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101059438. The current document aims to assess the project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities for the period between M6-M24. Based on the evaluation of the CDE activities and impact from the first period, this milestone aims also to provide an update to the project's plan for future CDE activities for the period between M24-M36.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

Effective communication is essential for maximizing the impact of the BioAgora project's results. By strategically disseminating information and engaging with stakeholders, the project can ensure that its findings and innovations reach the right audiences. This not only enhances the visibility of the project but also facilitates the practical application of its results, driving progress in biodiversity research and policy.

The updated plan for CDE activities will build on past successes and address identified challenges, ensuring that the BioAgora project continues to communicate its work effectively. This will help to achieve the project's goals and contribute to the broader objectives of achieving a fair and functional Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD).

This document is a crucial milestone for the BioAgora project, and it focuses on assessing the project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities. The primary goal of this milestone is to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of the project's CDE activities during the initial period of the project – M6-M24. By understanding what has worked well and what can be improved, the document also provides an update to the CDE plan of BioAgora, outlining the project's future CDE activities from M24 to M36.

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Introduction

BioAgora's Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC) underpins the necessary communication work needed for the successful implementation of the project, and attainment of its results. BioAgora's Key Exploitable Result (KER) is the Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD), part of the EU Biodiversity Knowledge Centre. Communication work by the project aims to amplify the project's recognition and visibility among stakeholders, and to foster the acceptance of SSBD by the target audiences as the main vehicle for knowledge exchange between science and policy in the EU. Guided by strategic CDE objectives for its target groups, the plan formulates key messages and ideas that BioAgora will communicate to support the implementation of the planned project actions and attainment of results.

In addition to being a strategic document, the PDEC serves as a practical guideline for the communication and dissemination activities, setting the BioAgora standards on how to conduct efficient communication, dissemination, and exploitation. The main communication tools used to promote the outputs of the BioAgora project are the project's website, newsletter, social media channels, and promotional materials. Also, project-specific CDE tools include policy briefs, factsheets, posters, media relationships, as well as events, such as conferences, workshops and business meetings, at which the project's ambition and results are demonstrated. The initial project PDEC provides a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for effective performance evaluation of the different CDE tools utilized within the project.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

BioAgora's Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC) (D.7.1) underpins the necessary communication work needed for the successful implementation of the project, and attainment of its results. BioAgora's Key Exploitable Result (KER) is the Science Service for Biodiversity (SSBD), part of the EU Biodiversity Knowledge Centre. Communication work by the project aims to amplify the project's recognition and visibility among stakeholders, and to foster the acceptance of SSBD by the target audiences as the main vehicle for knowledge exchange between science and policy in the EU. Guided by strategic CDE activities for its target groups, the plan formulates key messages and ideas that BioAgora communicates to support the implementation of the planned project actions and the dissemination of results.

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PDEC provides a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for effective performance evaluation of the different CDE tools utilized within the project.

Evaluation (M6-M24)

This milestone provides an analysis and evaluation of the first stage of the BioAgora project (M6-M24), which focused on building the initial community around the project. In this period, BioAgora established its network and started communicating and disseminating the project's first results. The evaluation presents cumulative progress in a tabular format (Table 1), presenting the tools and actions performed, target KPIs, achieved KPI results, as well as an evaluation and analysis of the achieved results. In addition, additional examples of high impact CDE activities are presented in the form of a list; to provide more detailed insights into what communication and dissemination activities typically consist of and what kind of audience is involved.

Table 1: Evaluation of BioAgora CDE activities, M6-M24

Tool and action	Target group	Target for M6-M24	Achieved result for M6-M24	Analysis and justification
BioAgora website	All	News items: 15/year Events in project calendar > 30 Users: 3000+ Geographical representation: > 30 countries	News items: 21/year Events in project calendar > 30 Users: 7700 Geographical representation: 118 countries	The website has generated a considerable amount of traffic, which proves for the initial interest towards BioAgora
Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube	All	Posts: 30/per year Followers: 1000 (X), 500 (LinkedIn)	Posts: >200 per year (X) >110 per year (LinkedIn) Followers: 727 (X) - over 60% of target 684 (LinkedIn) - 136% of target	With the number of Twitter followers KPI being set as 1000 during the period of technical report, the BioAgora project is currently at over 60% of the target. LinkedIn target is already achieved. For this reason, a two-step increase of social media KPIs is envisioned – one in M24-M36, and one in M36, when another update of the project's PDEC is due.

Promotional materials	All	150 downloads/item 50 distributed/per event	219 downloads total ~ 80 promotional materials distributed (per event where promotional materials have been distributed)	Promotional materials have not been physically distributed at all events where BioAgora attended. Creation of new promotional materials related to digital content – QR code BioAgora sticker – provides a bridge between promotional material distribution and
BioAgora Newsletter	All	3/year >300 subscribers	3/year 326 subscribers	The BioAgora newsletter has already met its KPI for total number of subscribers. To adapt to the growing attention to the project, the KPI for subscriber will be adjusted with the update of the PDEC.
Press relations and media coverage	All	Published PRs: 5 Views on EurekAlert! 2000/item Views on AlphaGalileo: 250/item	Published PRs: 1 Views on EurekAlert!: 2311	A press release on the launch of the BioAgora project was issued, ensuring that the beginning of the project is announced to a large audience.
Policy briefs	T#2, T#3	4/entire project	1 policy brief published Second policy brief in progress	With the target of 4 policy briefs for the entire duration of the project almost halfway met by M24, we realise that there is need for additional stressing on this dissemination tool. In the spirit of the future SSB, in the next period we envisage that BioAgora becomes a communications hub for policy briefs from other biodiversity related research initiatives.
Videos	All	Number of videos: 5 Combined views on YouTube: 700	7 videos uploaded > 1300 combined views	The BioAgora has achieved its goal for videos and has achieved its target combined views KPI. This is a positive development, which allows for the project to update its KPIs for the upcoming period and set a new, higher goal for views and video content creation.

Events (organised)	All	4/project duration >50 attendees/event	1 event organised until M24 >150 attendees/event	A detailed description of the BioAgora organised event is described in detail in the text below this table.
Sessions and workshops	T#1, T#2, T#3, T#4	N/A	6 workshops and sessions organised at conferences and events	A detailed description of the BioAgora organised sessions and workshops is described in detail in the text below this table.
Conferences	T#1, T#2, T#3, T#4	Number of conferences attended: ~ 15	Number of conferences attended: ~ 50	BioAgora members have participated in over 50 conferences throughout the initial period of the project, thus increasing the project's visibility.
Factsheets	All	5/project duration	N/A	Factsheets are envisioned to be created in the second half of the project's duration.

During the initial period of the project, the following significant BioAgora communication events were organised with the specific goal of increasing the outreach of the project. These initiatives have been pivotal in enhancing the project's visibility and engagement with key target groups. A list of these initiatives is provided below:

1. First BioAgora information event

Location: Online

Date: 16 April 2024

Outreach: > 150 attendees

Target groups: T#1, T#2, T#3 and T#4

This information event was especially targeted at EU-funded projects with a focus on biodiversity, and it aimed to showcase how the SSBD would benefit from the knowledge generated by the projects, and what possible cooperations with BioAgora exist. Representatives of over 70 EU-funded projects attended the event.

2. #WaterWiseEU social media campaign

Location: Online

Duration: May-September 2024

Description: The #WaterWiseEU campaign is a pivotal social media campaign of the EU in 2024, aimed to showcase the importance of freshwater conservation and efficient management of freshwater resources. BioAgora became part of this campaign, providing tailored social media content based on the project's Freshwater DC. The campaign features high value visual elements provided by partners from IGB Berlin and communicates tailored messages which stem from the output of Freshwater DC and strongly complements the general framework of the #WaterWiseEU campaign.

3. BioAgora became part of the Transformative change cluster

Location: Online

Duration: Throughout the project's lifetime

Description: The Transformative change cluster is a communications network which gathers 11 sister EU-funded projects on transformative change, amongst which the Transformative pathways, BIONEXT, BioTraCes, Biodiversa+, CO-OP4CBD, and RESPIN projects. This cooperation of project communication teams ensures the timely exchange of information and increasing of the outreach of project results.

4. BioAgora observers reported activities of the European Biodiversity Platform (EUBP) featured in the BioAgora newsletter

Location: Brussels

Duration: Throughout the project's lifetime

Description: BioAgora members who have observer status at the EUBP provided relevant information from the EUBP meetings for the BioAgora newsletter, thus ensuring that this important information about policy discussion reaches the newsletter subscribers.

5. BioAgora sessions at highly relevant events and conferences

Location: In-person, various countries

Duration: M6-M24

Description: The BioAgora project partners conducted several specially designed sessions and workshops at various high-impact conferences across the EU. Examples of such workshops organised are the special workshop on citizen science and its role in the biodiversity science-policy interface in the EU, organised at the 2024 ECSA conference by project partners from ESSRG and ECSA; the special BioAgora-facilitated session on biodiversity knowledge and policy at the 2024 World Biodiversity Forum, organised by UFZ and SYKE; the BioAgora workshop on connecting scientific knowledge to policy in the field of freshwater management at the 2024 FreeFlow conference, organised by IGB-Berlin; etc. These events provided a spotlight on the importance of connecting biodiversity knowledge and decision making and shed light on the opportunities of the future Science Service for Biodiversity.

Overall, activities and project outreach during the evaluated period (M6-M24) show that the BioAgora project established the essential building blocks of an efficient communications network, with the visibility of the project increasing steadily and solid connections of the project with other relevant stakeholders from various target groups being established. In the following section, a detailed implementation plan shows how the project will continue to develop the existing connections and expand towards new communication opportunities.

Implementation plan (M24-M36)

As BioAgora enters the next stage of the project's lifetime (M24-M36), the focus of CDE activities shifts significantly towards the active engagement of different target audiences (incl. enhanced participatory engagement) in the various cooperative tasks of the project, e.g. the creation and

growth of the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora stakeholder network. The implementation plan for CDE activities for this stage of the project is refined in accordance with the initially agreed-upon CDE activities in the project's grant agreement, the evaluation of CDE activities performed in M6-M24, as well as feedback received during the review process.

This stage will focus on deepening the interactions within the project community and broadening the scope of relevant stakeholders that can benefit from the project's output. The implementation plan of BioAgora CDE activities for the project's phase between M24-M36 is presented in Table 2 (below), and it provides the concrete measures BioAgora will undertake to communicate and disseminate its results from M24 to M36, as well as the KPIs by which their effectiveness will be measured.

Table 2: Implementation plan for M24-M36

Tool	Target group	Action in M24-M36	Target for M24-M36
BioAgora website	All	Update of the website to create new features, including FAQ section, Policy corner, and Synergies page.	3000 users > 50 countries
Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube	All	Create more synergies on social media with other key stakeholders (a particular focus on creating a set of communication clusters, such as the Transformative change cluster)	New followers in M24-M36: 1000 (X), 750 (LinkedIn)
Promotional materials	All	Creation of new promotional materials – sticker, brochure, factsheet, policy brief	150 downloads/item 50 distributed/per event
BioAgora Newsletter	All	Creation of new sections for the newsletter, focusing on focusing on scientific news relevant to policy and vice versa	3 newsletters for the period M24-M36 Additional 5-10% increase in subscribers
Press relations and media coverage	All	Press release about the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora aiming to increase the visibility of the newly launched network	1 PR
Policy briefs	T#2, T#3	The BioAgora project to issue one policy brief in the period M24-M36. For the next period, stronger emphasis will be made on the launching of the Policy	1 policy brief

		corner on the BioAgora website, where policy briefs from the project and from other biodiversity-related EU initiatives will be presented in a concise and convenient way.	
Videos	All	BioAgora is to create new video content, if possible - with a focus on the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora and on the Science Service for Biodiversity	2 videos 100 views on YouTube
Events (organised)	All	BioAgora is to continue organising events aiming to promote the functions. One such example is the science-policy interface training, scheduled to take place in 2025.	1 event
Conferences	T#1, T#2, T#3, T#4	BioAgora members proceed to participate in different conferences and forums, at which it will present the output of the project and the functions of the SSBD	5 conferences
Factsheets	All	The BioAgora factsheets are scheduled to be issued throughout the duration of the project. For the upcoming period M24-M36, work on the first BioAgora factsheet will begin.	1 factsheet in progress
Infographics	All	BioAgora will proceed to create a new infographic, describing the functions in period M24-M36.	1 infographic

For the upcoming period between M24-M36, BioAgora will focus on the creation of new dissemination outlets for both project results and broader science-policy interface dialogue within the field of biodiversity. A targeted update of the project website is scheduled to take part in M24-M36 to include three new sections – a tailored Policy corner which will feature biodiversity-related updates by policymakers and policy-relevant knowledge output by research projects and initiatives. The research projects and initiatives will be identified by the BioAgora project and will be contacted by the BioAgora project communications officers to provide relevant policy-related research outputs.

In accordance with the recommendations of the reviewers for RP1, the BioAgora project will also create a dedicated Synergies section on its website, which will display relevant projects and initiatives, with which the BioAgora project collaborates.

Also, a special FAQ section at the website is going to be launched to provide answers to frequently asked questions regarding BioAgora. Also, upon the recommendation of project reviewers, a Synergies section is also scheduled to be created on the website, with the list of potential synergies already defined in D7.1.

In M24-M36 the BioAgora project will also enhance its communication towards the development and increase of the Biodiversity Knowledge Agora. This is to be done through targeted communication campaigns through established communication channels and through tailored communication campaigns, including a special edition of the BioAgora newsletter and a special press release aiming to reach out to non-subscribers.

The project will also continue to develop its social media presence. With BioAgora gaining an increasing amount of attention on social media, a planned expansion of the project's follower base on X (formerly, Twitter) and LinkedIn is going to ensure the stable growth of the visibility and recognition of BioAgora on social media. Targeted communications campaigns, such as the ongoing #WaterWiseEU campaign, will aim to ensure the recognition of BioAgora's distinctive identity and key messages.

Conclusions and outlook

The BioAgora project is progressing steadily in terms of communication and dissemination activities. The efforts made thus far have kept the project on track, with all targets for the initial period (M6-M24) achieved. To accommodate the increasing demand for BioAgora content, some Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been adjusted for the upcoming period (M24-M36). New targets have been established to address the evolving needs and processes within the project.

During the initial phase, the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities primarily focused on community-building within the project and on the network of sister projects and initiatives. Moving forward, the emphasis of CDE activities will shift towards expanding outreach to a wider range of relevant stakeholders from the defined target groups. This strategic refocus is aligned with the BioAgora PDEC and it aims to enhance the visibility and impact of the project's outputs.

The performance metrics indicate that BioAgora is excelling in a number of the CDE targets, demonstrating the effectiveness of CDE strategies. To ensure the sustained success of the project's output, continued effort to meet and exceed the strategic goals outlined in the CDE plan are ensured in the next periods of the project's development.

References

Chakarova, R., Barov, B., Delbaere, B., & Voltz, M. (2022). Deliverable D7.1 Initial Plan for Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results. EU-HE BIO-Agora Project, Grant agreement No 101059438.

